

pH values are consistent with the fact that Rajmahal volcanics are predominantly basic.

The observed i.r. and X-ray data have been tabulated in Tables 3 and 4 and a comparison of the observed data with reported values confirm the presence of Montmorillonite clay mineral in all the samples along with Kaolinite in minor proportions.

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Studies in the Synthesis of Anticancer Agents : Part IV. Nitrogen Mustards of 9-Phenanthroyl Chlorides

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It is generally considered that the nitrogen mustards owe their antitumour activity to their ability to cyclise to the highly reactive ethylenimonium ions(I) in polar solvents such as water¹. This cyclisation cannot occur if a proton is coordinated with the nitrogen atom. Hence, nitrogen mustards are relatively stable in dilute aqueous solutions and at the physiological pH². The resulting ethylenimonium ions or in the case of ethylenimines or epoxides, the polarisable three membered rings react with compounds containing a readily replaceable hydrogen atom such as in the free amino group of nucleic acids etc. The weakly basic aromatic

nitrogen mustards may react with nucleophilic biological systems by way of a carbonium ion intermediate, since their cyclic ethylenimonium forms are relatively unstable, probably by a cross linking mechanism.

In continuation of our work on studies in the synthesis of nitrogen mustards as anticancer agents³⁻⁵ we report in this paper the synthesis of nitrogen mustards from 9-phenanthroyl chloride⁶ and 2, 3, 6-trimethoxy-9-phenanthroyl chloride and also their anticancer activity.

9-Phenanthroyl chloride(II) on condensation with N, N-bis(2-chloroethyl)amine⁷ afforded phenanthrene-9-[N,N-bis(2-chloroethylenimonium)] carboxamide ion(III). I.R. spectrum of (III) showed a strong band at 1722 cm⁻¹ supporting the ethylenimonium structure. 2,3,6-Trimethoxy-9-phenanthroyl chloride (IIa) on similar condensation with N,N-bis(2-chloroethyl)amine gave [N,N-bis(2-chloroethyl)-2,3,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene-9-carboxamide(IV) which showed a band at 1647 cm⁻¹ in its i.r. spectrum. This on further crystallisation from aqueous ethanol rearranged to 2,3,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene-9-[N,N-bis(2-chloroethylenimonium)] carboxamide ion(IIIa), which showed a strong band at 1700 cm⁻¹ indicating that rearrangement has taken place during crystallisation from aqueous ethanol.

(II) R = R₁ = R₂ = H

(IIa) R = R₁ = R₂ = OCH₃

(III) $R=R_1=R_2=H$
 (IIIa) $R=R_1=R_2=OCH_3$

(IV) $R=R_1=R_2=OCH_3$

Experimental

Melting points as reported are uncorrected. I.R. spectrum (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 457 grating spectrophotometer.

Phenanthrene-9-[(N,N-bis(2-chloroethylenimonium)) Carboxamide ion(III)]:

A suspension of N,N-bis(2-chloroethyl) amino-hydrochloride (2.0 g.) in benzene (25 ml) was shaken with sodium hydroxide (0.5 g in 10 ml water); benzene layer was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, concentrated to half its volume and chilled to 5°. A benzene solution of 9-phenanthrolyl chloride prepared from phenanthrene-9-carboxylic acid (1 g) and thionyl chloride (2 ml) was added dropwise to the above solution with stirring. A white solid began to separate within a few minutes and after the addition of the acid chloride was complete, the mixture was stirred in a cold water bath for 30 minutes and then at the room temperature for further 30 minutes. The whole reaction mixture was then refluxed for 3 hr and allowed to stand overnight at the room temperature. It was then filtered and the light yellow filtrate treated, with decolourising carbon, concentrated to 5 ml and left at the room temperature for 2 hr. The solution was then heated just to boiling and diluted carefully with petroleum ether which left a gummy product. It was purified by chromatographing over alumina using benzene as an eluent. The solvent was evaporated in vacuum and the resulting product crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 208-10°, yield 0.65 g (40%). (Found: C, 65.66; H, 4.88; N, 4.22 $C_{19}H_{17}NOCl_2$ requires C, 65.90; H, 4.91; N, 4.66%).

Phenanthrene-9-[N,N-bis(2-chloroethyl)] 2,3,6-trimethoxycarboxamide(IV):

2,3,6-Trimethoxyphenanthrolyl chloride, prepared from 2,3,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene-9-carboxylic

acid^a (0.6 g) was condensed with N,N-bis(2-chloroethyl) amino-hydrochloride (1.2 g) as above and the reaction mixture worked up as before. The product was crystallised from a benzene-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 166-67°, yield 0.5 g (59%). (Found: C, 60.20; H, 5.68; N, 3.45% $C_{22}H_{22}NO_4Cl_2$ requires: C, 60.54; H, 5.28; N, 3.21%). When it was further crystallised in aqueous ethanol, the m.p. changed to 134°.

Biological Screening:

Phenanthrene-9-[N, N-bis(2-chloroethylenimonium)]-carboxamide ions(III) and (IV) were tested against Rat Walker 256 Carcinoma and showed the following results:

Compound	Dose	Survivors	T/C%
(III)	7.5 mg/kg	6/6	90
(IV)	10 mg/kg	6/6	91

This indicates that compounds show significant anticancer activity.

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